
Anchoring the Modern Approach of the World's Freshwater Laboratory in the Traditional Anishinaabe Worldview

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ABSTRACT

A contemporary natural scientist typically describes water as “colorless, odorless, tasteless, a universal solvent” that “exists in different phases” and “is built of molecules of two hydrogens and one oxygen,” whereas an Anishinaabe Elder who carries Traditional Knowledge considers water as “a spirit, a living being” that “gives life and takes life” and “is sent down from the sky to bring forth provision.” What happens when these two worldviews meet? Despite recent efforts in academia to bring Indigenous knowledge from the peripheries to the center stage, we still find Western models dominate. This paper aimed to amplify Indigenous knowledge—specifically Anishinaabe teachings from the heart of colonial Canada—and center it within modern scientific discourse in the field of freshwater research. IISD Experimental Lakes Area (IISD-ELA) is uniquely situated in the boreal forests of northwestern Ontario, Canada, on the traditional lands of the Anishinaabe people. For over 55 years, the whole ecosystem approach at IISD-ELA has pushed the envelope of our understanding of many environmental challenges that impact fresh water. IISD-ELA’s engagement of local knowledge keepers on the ground, in the real world, in contrast to the theoretical, attempts to re-evaluate the ecologies of two distinct knowledge systems and break through conventional conceptualizations of worldviews. This paper concludes a dire need for a paradigm shift in

acquiring knowledge in the conscious minds of scientists. It provides practical lessons and insights gained through the example of a science community traversing the middle path.

Keywords: Anishinaabe, indigenous knowledge, science, water,

MIIGWECH MANITO

Miigwech Manito, meaning “Thank you, Creator (Great Spirit),” is the way Anishinaabe Elders and knowledge carriers initiate a speech or blessing at a ceremony, a gathering, or an event. Therefore, *Miigwech Manito*.

During an opening ceremony, an Anishinaabe Elder would first introduce himself, including his spirit name, his clan, and his *doodem* (or totem). In most cases, the Elder then invites everyone present also to introduce themselves. The reason why the spirit name, clan, and *doodem* are included in an introduction is that, as Memashkawigaabaw, a language helper from Nigigoon-siminikaaning First Nation, said, “Anishinaabe people will be asked about these three things when they pass on to the Spirit World” (Memashkawigaabaw, personal communication, December 2024).

From a worldly perspective, self-introduction is the beginning of a relationship. It conveys messages about who we are (*do I know you?*) and how we are, as in our ways of being and doing, our cultures and customs, and our manners and etiquettes (*can I trust you?*). More often, we look for instant connection if we share a similar worldview (*can I relate to you?*).

Orientally raised and occidentally educated, I am often confronted with different, sometimes opposing, perspectives. Clashes of these perspectives have exposed me to different bodies of knowledge and helped cultivate in me a curious mind. This is an attempt to put into words the lessons and insights that have been accumulated walking across the world.

INTRODUCTION

The problem of inserting Indigenous knowledge into West-

ern frameworks has become a focal point of critique and reflection in scholarly discourse. The fate of Indigenous knowledge when confronting the dominant Eurocentric paradigms often ends up being either outright denied or superficially adopted or shape-shifted into something unrecognizable as a result of assimilation (Ahenakew, 2016; Santos, 2014; Smith, 1999).

Santos' concept of "epistemicide" paints a devastating picture of the suppression and erasure of non-Western ways of knowing and being by the colonial powers (Santos, 2014). For centuries, Indigenous Peoples struggled to preserve the ways of their ancestors, and many took them underground (according to testimonies I often hear from Indigenous Peoples). With these alternative perspectives resurfacing and re-entering our dialogues, there is a clash of worldviews. The dominant ideals that focus on development, accumulation, and progress dictate that we jump to quick fixes for the sake of knowledge production and attempt to "graft" Indigenous knowledge onto the branches of the Western paradigm, and in doing so, we risk distorting the ways of the ancestors (Andreotti et al., 2011; Ahenakew, 2016).

The explorative work of these scholars points to the challenge *not* of inclusion or integration by planting Indigenous knowledge in foreign soil; rather, it invites us to critically analyze and reflect on the framework in which we ground ourselves (Ahenakew, 2016; Andreotti et al., 2011). When the "grafting" of Indigenous knowledge is made visible, it becomes clear that Indigenous knowledge is either being reduced to a set of categories that is filtered through the Western lens or is induced into the Western tendencies of universalizing knowledge (Ahenakew, 2016; Lombard, 2022). Both are a result of a lack of true reflection on our worldviews, as well as a lack of deep humility toward alternative perspectives.

Worldviews and Modes of Knowledge Acquisition

A worldview is a foundational lens through which individuals and communities interpret and understand the world around them and their places in it (Berkes, 2012). It is often shaped by language, culture, and experience, and it forms a web of intricate values, beliefs, and relationships (Whorf, 1956). Indigenous worldviews are known to be relational and spiritual, whereas Western paradigms often prioritize objectivity and utili-

ty (Smith, 1999). The contrast becomes particularly pronounced in the *management of the natural resources* as described in a Western perspective, as opposed to *reciprocal relationships with all relatives* in an Indigenous view of the world. The contrast is not only in the linguistic expression but also in the ontological positioning of oneself. Indigenous epistemology positions humans *not* as separate from nature but as integral members of vast and interconnected worlds of both the seen and the unseen (McGregor, 2014).

This conceptual and epistemological divide between Western and Indigenous worldviews has profound implications for the mechanisms or modes of acquiring knowledge (Lumbard, 2024) as a mode of knowledge acquisition, science or scientific method entails a systemic and robust process of inquiry through questioning, observing, experimenting, analyzing, and concluding to investigate natural phenomena (Hepburn & Andersen, 2021). This mode of knowledge inquiry is extremely useful in gaining a better and clearer understanding of a study object in a controlled, observable, and measurable environment. In this paper, I intentionally avoid using “Western science,” a term that is still widely adopted and implies scientific contributions attributed solely to the West (Kayumova & Dou, 2022). It is also argued that the origin of scientific methodology can be traced back and linked to non-Western traditions (Castillo, 2013). Therefore, the term “Western science” is used to limit science within the paradigms of Western-centred thinking. However, my caution in using “Western science” in no way minimizes the contributions that the West has made in scientific fields.

Knowledge and Ethics

Western paradigms are often critiqued for their lack of ethical dimensions in knowledge production and for treating research pursuits as a detached process of discovery rather than a relational stance of care and a reciprocal act of protection (Gross et al., 2023; Smith, 1999). In contrast, ethics and moral responsibilities are inherently linked to the growth of knowledge in Indigenous worldviews (Andreotti et al., 2011; Smith, 1999). Lumbard critiques the separation of ethics from knowledge and ar-

gues that *true* knowledge is inseparable from ethical acts and that ethics must be lived and practiced to gain *true* knowledge (Lumbard, 2022). This line of thinking is much like the Anishinaabe moral framework provided by the teachings of *bimaa-diziwin* (the “good life”) or the Seven Sacred Laws of wisdom, love, respect, courage, honesty, humility, and truth, which are acts of good (way of being) on a day-to-day basis that leads to good knowledge (way of knowing) (Gross et al., 2023; Ruml, 2012). In simple words, doing good—as in being good to the land and the water, the plants and the animals, and the seen and the unseen—leads to knowledge. This mode of acquiring knowledge is in stark contrast with the knowledge that is gained through separation, compartmentalization, and accumulation, in which there exists an ethical void.

The deliberation of the interlink among worldviews, modes of acquiring knowledge, and moral values can foster a paradigm shift, especially in scientists, researchers, and educators who primarily operate within a Western framework. This paper is my attempt to encourage colleagues who work with knowledge from a Western perspective to reflect on their - epistemological assumptions and to reimagine the possibilities of anchoring science, scientific methods, research, and education in Indigenous worldviews of relational, responsible, and reciprocal ways of knowing and being while being mindful of the potential risk of pruning diverse ecosystems of knowledge into conformity. To achieve this, I will present the lessons and insights gained from the unique case of the IISD Experimental Lakes Area (IISD-ELA, www.iisd.org/ela), a freshwater science facility stationed on the ancestral lands of the Anishinaabe people, as it navigates the journey of engaging with local knowledge. Can IISD-ELA see its reflection in the still waters of Anishinaabe perspectives? My methodology for addressing this question is to weave together stories of key moments of reflection from this journey. In doing so, I assert that the scientific endeavors of IISD-ELA will thrive with greater vitality when nourished and steered by the profound Anishinaabe wisdom on water and other relatives.

About Treaty #3 and IISD-ELA

There were 70 treaties signed in the span of more than 200 years from 1701 to 1923 between the European settlers and Indigenous Peoples who resided on the land now known as Canada (Daugherty, 1986). The political reality of the mid-19th century propelled the British to enter into agreements with the Saulteaux, one of the four groups of the Anishinaabe, in order to establish their presence from Fort Garry to Fort William (known today as Winnipeg, Manitoba, and Thunder Bay, Ontario, respectively) (Daugherty, 1986; Grand Council Treaty #3, 2025). Signed on October 3, 1873, Treaty #3 allowed the British to proceed with their plan to build a route that traversed the territory through a web of rivers and lakes, among other things (Grand Council Treaty #3, 2025). The negotiation also allowed the *unceded* land and the resources to be shared between the Anishinaabe and the British within the territory of 55,000 square miles (see Figure 1-a) (Daugherty, 1986; Grand Council Treaty #3, 2025).

There are 28 Anishinaabe communities in the traditional territory of Treaty #3 (Grand Council Treaty #3, 2025). The word *Anishinaabe* is used interchangeably with *Ojibwe* as a distinct identity. *Ojibwe* also refers to the language known as Anishinaabemowin, which is the Anishinaabe language.

Figure 1

- (a) Map of Treaty #3, which includes 28 Anishinaabe communities;
- (b) Map of IISD-ELA

Source: (a) Grand Council Treaty #3, 2025, with permission; (b) IISD-ELA.

Memashkawigaabaw, the language helper from Nigigoonsiminkaaning First Nation, shared his search for the meaning of *Anishinaabe*:

I like to joke about the word *Anishinaabe* when I introduce myself. I say, 'I'm not Anishinaabe; I am *onizhishinaabe*.' The laughter that follows helps me identify who the language speakers are because *onizhishi* means "handsome" or "nice-looking," and *aabe* refers to a male. It's a playful twist, but there's a connection to the meaning of *Anishinaabe*. While *Anishinaabe* generally refers to human beings or *Nenaboozhoo*—the original man—it also carries the idea of a process. The *Ani-* prefix signifies something in the process of becoming; *shina-* refers to being lowered; and *aabe* points to the male of a species. This all ties back to the creation story of *Nenaboozhoo*, whose spirit was lowered from the sky and born into the world. (Memashkawigaabaw, personal communication, January 2025)

Consisting of 58 small-bodied pristine lakes and their watersheds (see Figure 1-b), Experimental Lakes Area was founded in 1968 by a group of limnologists who were determined to gain a better understanding of the then-much-debated issue of algal blooms. ELA is unique for two reasons: 1) it is a scientific facility remotely situated in the boreal forest of the province of Ontario, in colonial Canada, as well as in the heart of Treaty #3 Traditional Lands of the Anishinaabe people (see Figure 1-a), and 2) the whole ecosystem approach that ELA adopted to tackle freshwater issues is both innovative and transformative. For over 55 years, scientists and researchers at ELA have been implementing this approach to conduct experiments to uncover the impact humans have on inland lakes, leading to many groundbreaking discoveries in our understanding of environmental challenges that freshwater faces, such as acid rain, mercury contamination, oil spills, and so on.

In 2014, the ELA facility experienced a historic transition from being a federally run institution to a not-for-profit subsidiary of the International Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD), an international think tank based in Canada as a subsidiary of IISD. The research station was rebranded as IISD-ELA. Since then, IISD-ELA has welcomed new opportunities and im-

aginations to expand its mandate in scientific endeavors, education, and communications.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology of this paper centers on reflection, a means of breaking through the surface and peering into what lies beneath. Reflection is also an opportunity to pause and carefully examine experiences, perspectives, and questions to make connections, deepen understanding, and gain clarity. Looking back on nearly a decade of immersion in the teachings of local Elders and knowledge keepers on the one hand and communicating IISD- ELA's science and research to the communities on the other, the moments of reflection have helped conceptualize and make sense of the intersections of multiple ways of knowing and being. IISD-ELA's approach to fostering relationships with Indigenous communities in Treaty #3 allows for dedicated and open-ended engagement, unburdened by rigid agendas. It involves attending community gatherings, participating in ceremonies, and collaborating on the ground to co-create projects that foster learning and sharing.

People and Place

Nestled deep within the boreal forests and surrounded by hundreds of lakes, the IISD-ELA facility serves as a hub for scientists, researchers, and students from various fields of hydrology, meteorology, biology, toxicology, and so on (see Figure 2). During the open-water season, this vibrant community comes together to implement the whole-ecosystem approach to experimental research through dosing, sampling, testing, and analyzing, all aimed at improving our understanding of the complex challenges facing freshwater ecosystems.

While the deliberate change or addition of substances to the experimental lakes—mainly within mesocosms as well as across entire lakes—is a unique practice that attracts the curiosity of scientists and researchers, it also exposes water to continuous handling, examination, and alteration. This reality under-

mines a profound responsibility to honor water from an Anishinaabe perspective. Therefore, guided by the wisdom of local Elders, ceremonies were introduced to ensure that the work is conducted with respect, humility, and a steadfast commitment to preserving the integrity of water. IISD-ELA now hosts an annual Spring Nibi Ceremony (*nibi* means “water” in Ojibwe) and a Fall Feast, which invite people from all walks of life to join in the sacred practices led by Elders. In these ceremonies, the Elders lift and bless the water, surrounded by those who, through their daily work with these lakes, often find themselves bonding with the waters they tend to.

Figure 2

Aerial Photo of the IISD-ELA facility

Source: IISD-ELA.

Through the organic process of immersing in local experiences—active listening, observing, and learning—two key moments of reflection stand out. My intention in sharing these moments is to highlight the key instances that prompted reflection on the concepts of worldviews, ways of acquiring knowledge, and moral responsibilities discussed in the Introduction. My interpretation of some of the teachings may contain inaccuracies, given the inherent barriers in different languages and worldviews, and I welcome any corrections.

Reflection 1: “Water is living.”

In Anishinaabe cultures, *nibi* is held in high regard. People get together to honor *nibi* through gatherings, water walks, and ceremonies that lift and advocate for water. These events, often organized and led by women Elders, are centered entirely around *nibi*. Each gathering begins with an Elder speaking in Anishinaabemowin, setting the tone in a good way. For those of us unfamiliar with the language, an English translation follows. The Elder gives thanks to the Creator for sending the water and expresses gratitude for its life-sustaining power. Water is described *repeatedly* as a living spirit, a sacred entity that both gives and takes life. The Elder also calls attention to all our relatives—human, plant, and animal—and the sacred web of relationships that bind us to water. With reverence and urgency, the Elder reminds us of our responsibility to water, affirming that the Creator entrusted the Anishinaabe people as the custodians and guardians of *nibi* and all other beings.

Some ceremonies include the sacred meeting of *nibi*, where waters gathered from different parts of the region and nation, and even from around the world, are brought together and mixed as a symbol of the unity of all waters as one body. It reflects the connection of all waters and that when one body of water suffers, the pain is felt across the whole. At times, *nibi* songs, the ancient melodies passed through generations or gifted in the dreams of knowledge carriers, are sung to the steady rhythm of drums or the shake of rattles. These songs are expressions and acts of connection, a way to speak to *nibi* and invoke its healing.

When fluent Ojibwe speakers shift to English to convey water teachings, there's sometimes a noticeable hesitation, as if words falter at the tip of the tongue. These moments reveal how much is lost in translation, how the essence of these teachings is deeply rooted in Anishinaabemowin, and how English falls short of capturing their true depth and meaning. The gap between the two languages became especially apparent during a translation exercise when we attempted to translate IISD-ELA's research into Anishinaabemowin. This will be explored further in Reflection 2.

The deep connections that exist among water, humans and all living beings were encapsulated in the creation of the Treaty #3 Nibi Declaration, a framework for water advocacy grounded in Anishinaabe laws and values. Shaped by the voices of community members, the declaration was presented in a ceremony and honored with a feast before being formally printed and bound, affirming its sacred and communal significance. The Nibi Declaration gives voice to the voiceless—water. As the custodians of *nibi*, a responsibility bestowed by the Creator, the Anishinaabe people speak on its behalf, proclaiming that water holds inherent rights and must be respected, protected, and cherished as a living entity.

The connection among all relatives that the Anishinaabe people speak of transcends time. In a collaborative project with Sagkeeng First Nation, we explored the interconnectedness between the community and the land. As industrial development encroaches, ecological loss has been inseparably tied to cultural erosion. The decline of nature's elements often reflects the fading of traditions, customs, and cultural practices. A few community members recalled the removal of old trees. They remarked on the loss of connection to their ancestors: "Some trees were ancient in age, thousands of years old, [and were] friends to our ancestors" (Anonymous community member, personal communication, December 2022).

Reflection 2: "The air that the trees breathe."

In an effort to minimize the language barrier in communicating IISD-ELA's research and out of curiosity about expressing scientific findings in Anishinaabemowin, we embarked on translating key research conclusions into Ojibwe. One such study focuses on climate change through a diversion project designed to mimic water level fluctuations in lakes. We quickly realized that many scientific terms, like carbon dioxide (CO₂), did not have direct equivalents in Ojibwe. To explain this, we delved into the nature of what CO₂ is, describing it as a compound of one carbon atom, the foundation of all life, and two oxygen atoms.

One Elder, after patiently listening to our explanation, asked, "What does CO₂ do?" After a moment of reflection, we

replied, “CO₂ is the gas we exhale, and it sustains plants.” This simple exchange ignited a shared “aha!” moment. The Ojibwe speakers, with new clarity, visualized the movement of CO₂ and crafted an Ojibwe interpretation: *mitigoo-inanaamowin*. Its English translation in reverse means “the air that the trees breathe.” For the rest of us, it was a moment of shifting from defining what something *is* to seeing what something *does*.

mitigoo-inanaamowin ni carbon dioxide

mitig = tree

in = thus; in a certain direction; in a certain manner

anaamo = breathe; use the voice

win = noun forming final

The same process unfolded when translating research on mercury contamination in fish. The term for mercury emerged as *biiwaabikowaabo gaa-waawaageshkaag*, reversed to “a liquid metal that shines brightly” in English. In witnessing these translation sessions and observing the language and its speakers, we have learned that Anishinaabemowin is creational, constantly renewing itself without relying on foreign terms. It is not just a means of communication but a vessel for culture and spirituality, inherently carrying teachings, traditions, and values. As Memashkawigaabaw once shared, some Elders speak “spiritual Ojibwe,” a form of the language that is “loaded with culture” and remains “untouched by residential schools.” Anishinaabemowin is also action-based, in contrast to the noun-heavy structure of languages like English. This focus on acts mirrors the Anishinaabe teachings that urge responsibility, commitment, and direct action to protect the land and the water.

biiwaabikowaabo gaa-waawaageshkaag ni-v mercury

biiwaabiko = metal iron

waabo = liquid

gaa-waawaageshkaag = it is bright/shiny

Countless pivotal moments have shaped these reflections, sometimes long, meaningful conversations with Elders, friends, and colleagues, who have helped shed light on fragments of these teachings. Beyond the surface, there are individuals deeply committed to restoring ancestral ways, preserving and revitalizing language and culture, and safeguarding the well-being of the land and the water for the survival

of the seventh generation. Many Elders carry and share teachings passed down from those before them, with variations that reflect regional differences, making it impossible to attribute specific words to specific individuals. To protect confidentiality, names and identifiable details have been omitted, except for Memashkawigaabaw, whose spirit name is included with his permission.

In the next section, I will synthesize these experiences and teachings to develop a broader understanding of the various ways of acquiring knowledge. The discussion will examine whether IISD-ELA's practices align with or are perhaps challenged by Anishinaabe perspectives, particularly in how knowledge is gained, relationships are cultivated, and responsibilities are upheld.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

These encounters between worldviews reveal key insights into different modes of knowledge acquisition and highlight the potential for a pluralistic approach to foster transformative dialogue.

The source and mechanism of knowledge acquisition can vary significantly. The scientific approach of IISD-ELA, like any other scientific method, relies on empirical observation and experimentation to address challenges in freshwater systems. The knowledge that the Anishinaabe people carry stems from lived experiences of listening to, conversing with, and learning from *nibi*, which is regarded *not* as a resource but as a relative, a living entity imbued with dignity and honor, deserving of care and protection.

The whole-ecosystem approach of IISD-ELA provides data-driven evidence to inform decision-making in a world dominated by human influence. Anishinaabe advocacy gives voice to water, challenging the utilitarian and anthropocentric worldviews that overlook non-human existence. A holistic approach is made possible by valuing the strengths of both ways of knowing while resisting the one-size-fits-all imposition of epistemic dominance.

This ensures that moral responsibilities toward water are honored.

A shift in perspective occurs when these diverse ways of knowing are brought into dialogue. It is in this convergence that true awareness arises, encouraging practitioners of science and research to recognize that their methods are not the sole pathway to knowledge but one among many equally valuable approaches rooted in ethics and relations.

Deep Dive Into Modes of Knowledge Acquisition

Figure 3 was created to help us visualize different modes of knowledge acquisition. There can be many other mechanisms in other knowledge systems; for the sake of relevance, this discussion focuses only on the three presented here.

Knowledge can be gained through reciprocal relationships, as shown in Figure 3-a, where land, animals, plants, and water are not viewed as objects of study but as teachers in their rights. They offer knowledge about themselves and their roles within the broader web of life, and their teachings are recognized and understood by the Anishinaabe people.

Figure 3

Modes of Acquiring Knowledge

Source: Author.

This differs from observational learning (see Figure 3-c), where the observer is separated from the observed, and

knowledge is acquired by studying an object's behavior, such as watching a beaver build a dam to understand its actions and their consequences. In contrast, when the beaver is acknowledged as a teacher, the knowledge exchange is no longer one-sided. The beaver imparts its instinctual knowledge, revealing its role in maintaining balance in the natural world. This concept of a non-human teacher can be unsettling to a science-oriented mind that's accustomed to analyzing the natural world through data and numbers.

Moreover, knowledge is not acquired in isolation from action but through ethical engagement with the relatives by acting with care and respect toward land, water, plants, and animals. Thus, knowing and doing are inseparable. Knowledge is formed and accumulated through good acts by treating all relatives with kindness and respect. This aligns with the action-based nature of Anishinaabemowin, which emphasizes responsibilities. As a learner working to recover the Ojibwe language, Memashkawigaabaw reflects on how a strong grasp of the language has transformed his view of nature, stating, "I started seeing things move through Anishinaabemowin" (Memashkawigaabaw, personal communication, February 2024).

Manito Aki Inaakonigewin, the Great Earth Law of Treaty #3, like many other Anishinaabe laws, is from the Creator (Grand Council Treaty #3, 2023). It states that "law-making comes from the Creator's way of life, passed on through ancestral stories, songs, and teachings." (Grand Council Treaty #3, 2023). As shown in Figure 3-b, human beings are gifted with the intellect to learn and build relationships within creation, recognizing that we are part of it. The Creator's law doesn't prioritize human rights. Still, it emphasizes the rights of all relatives, assigning humans the responsibility to care for them.

The interactions among the created transcend physicality. Anishinaabe Elders often speak of making offerings to spirits (beings from the unseen world). The ceremony, therefore, holds meaning on multiple levels: it is an act of honoring our relatives and doing right by them while also inviting the good spirits from the unseen world to assist in caring for the well-being of all creations. This again challenges a secular mind that only acknowl-

edges the observable world.

It's worth clarifying that highlighting the differences among these mechanisms of knowledge acquisition is not to determine which is superior or inferior. The approach shown in Figure 3-c is valuable for honing in on compartments, and it is through this method that we have gained a detailed understanding of water at its molecular level as H₂O. However, by acknowledging other ways of acquiring knowledge, we ensure that we don't become so absorbed in dissecting the parts that we lose sight of the whole.

Reflecting on IISD-ELA's Approach

IISD-ELA's approach to freshwater research is innovative in integrating multiple compartments of freshwater science, offering a comprehensive investigation often missing in isolated lab-based studies. This holistic method, in a way, reflects the interconnectedness central to the Anishinaabe worldview. Technological advancements also shape research practices, and with improved testing technology, IISD-ELA has pioneered non-lethal fish sampling, which is a more ethical way to work with animals. Thus, grounding scientific practices in the ethical framework of Anishinaabe teachings promotes the development of responsible technological applications in research, moving beyond purely utilitarian outcomes.

As mentioned in the Methodology, ceremonies at IISD-ELA act as a reminder for scientists, researchers, and students to honor water and build a deeper connection with the lakes they study. Participating in these ceremonies encourages active reflection on water's significance, and some have begun making offerings to the lakes, with the Elders' permission, before proceeding with sampling activities.

While it is promising to see a shift in how Anishinaabe perspectives are perceived, the challenge lies in making these ways of knowing more visible and present in the awareness of those within IISD-ELA. In the next section, I will summarize the discussions and offer recommendations for IISD-ELA's ongoing engagement with local knowledge, as well as for others working with knowledge who may find these insights beneficial.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The scientific method follows a structured process of inquiry. Therefore, advocating for a pluralistic approach does not mean altering scientific practices but reconsidering their positioning. There is an opportunity to reimagine and root it in the moral codes of Indigenous worldviews. In the context of IISD-ELA, this means anchoring the whole ecosystem practice of freshwater science within the Anishinaabe ethical framework to foster connections with the lakes, land, trees, fish, and all other beings. How can this be done?

Scientific methods are taught and implemented by people—scientists, researchers, and educators—who bring their assumptions and ways of understanding the world into their work. Thus, the shift is about reshaping the mindset of those who practice them through creating space for the encounter of worldviews, where discomfort is embraced, difficult questions are asked, and mistakes become part of the learning process. More than just an intellectual exercise, this process invites scientists, researchers, and educators to engage with Indigenous perspectives in a way that is relational and experiential.

A key aspect of the Anishinaabe worldview is that understanding the world cannot be separated from living in harmony with it. This perspective demands more than intellectual recognition of the significance of water—it requires action. Participation in ceremonies offers a tangible way to move beyond verbal commitments, embodying respect for water, land, and all relatives. While the spiritual connections formed through ceremonies may be elusive or challenging to grasp from a secular perspective, they remain essential in cultivating an ethical and relational approach to knowledge.

For scientists, researchers, and colleagues working at the intersection of multiple worldviews, it is essential to recognize the paradigms that shape their approach to knowledge. Engagement with diverse knowledge systems should be approached with humility and a willingness to learn, resisting the impulse to impose a dominant framework. It is also crucial to actively seek ways to mend and strengthen relationships with water, plants,

animals, and all beings involved in research, guided by the ethical framework inherent in Indigenous worldviews.

To conclude on the topic of water, I invite readers to reflect on the United Nations resolution that recognizes that everyone has the right to access clean water, acknowledging the fundamental human right to clean water and highlighting a significant global issue. Is there space to also recognize the rights of water? Could we complete this resolution, which has now been in place for over a decade, by adding what has long been missing—that everyone has the *right* to access clean water? Everyone has the *responsibility* to protect and care for water. Perhaps, by repairing our relationship with water, we will uncover new insights and approaches to address this ongoing and persistent issue.

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